

THE IMPORTANCE OF IDIOMS IN TEACHING SPEAKING

Nesipbaeva Saodatkhon

English teacher at school №55 in Kegeyli, Karakalpakstan

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Annotation: The value of idioms in enhancing speaking has been demonstrated in the article. Additionally, a variety of strategies for enhancing learners' speaking and idiom comprehension abilities have been provided.

Keywords: idioms, teaching method, teaching speaking, speaking and idioms.

The demand for the English language is growing every day over the globe these days. As a result, there is a clear need for skilled language teachers as well as innovative, more efficient teaching techniques. There have been many approaches given in this area so far, and they all initially appear to be useful. Speaking is one of the most crucial language abilities, and most language learners are eager to learn how to talk as fluently as a native speaker. There are various ways to learn to talk, but not all of them will necessarily produce the finest outcomes. The similar outcome is seen in the teaching process, when instructors occasionally struggle to teach speaking in a creative, communicative way. The success of teaching and speaking is the intended goal for both students and teachers.

Knowing how to communicate in the target language is, as we all know, one of the fundamental objectives of language instruction.

Idioms unquestionably play a significant role in languages and cultures all over the world. Idioms are challenging for English as a Second Language (ESL) students because their meanings might change at any time. When faced with idioms, for instance, non-native speakers may find themselves in hot water. Idioms are a barrier to learning English for many ESL or English as a foreign language, or EFL, students.

Context plays a crucial part in language learning. EFL students frequently lack a solid understanding of the multiple definitions of new vocabulary in diverse settings. Because of this, EFL students struggle to use the language they have learnt in real-world situations. For pupils to learn and practise their language, teachers must first give a rich environment. For instance, adolescents' understanding of idioms is improved by linguistic contextual information.

The context provided by a word can aid readers in understanding what it means. Contrarily, readers will find it challenging to tolerate language that lacks context. As a result, learning language in meaningful situations is more beneficial for EFL students than learning isolated words through memorization and drilling.

For many years, it has been common practise to utilise stories to instruct and amuse language-learning students. Students are typically attracted to and easily immersed in interesting stories. It is crucial for EFL teachers to give students rich context since it is extremely efficient at assisting pupils in learning English idioms. Thus, including English idioms in engaging stories may aid EFL students in better understanding and remembering them.

Discussing what they read with one another is a good way for students to improve their understanding. Group discussions can offer students several chances to develop the social and linguistic skills they need to comprehend any new materials they come across. During content

reading, ESL students participate in group conversations where they help one another understand difficult vocabulary, grasp the key ideas, and respond to questions about what they read. Therefore, it appears that group discussion is a useful method for improving students' reading comprehension.

Students share knowledge and voice their opinions regarding idioms during group discussions. Group conversations help students improve their speaking skills, and they aim to add colour to their speech and utterances by using newly learnt idioms.

Since learning English idioms is essential for EFL learners in order to master the language, it is crucial that EFL teachers create numerous activities that allow students to effectively apply English idioms in their learning. Additionally, students benefit from collaborative activities since they may interact with peers and share the enjoyment of learning. Finally, students can apply English idioms in four skills when teachers include listening, speaking, reading, and writing tasks in their idiom instruction. As a result, it is effective to teach English idioms to EFL students when they are given a variety of tasks to practise and use English idioms in varied circumstances.

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